

Critical Analysis of the Status of Health Education

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Abstract

Health education is the key factor for the growth of human society from the ancient time. Ancient Greeks were the pioneers of health education. Health Education encompasses combination of principles by which the individuals and communities are imparted knowledge to behave in a manner that is favorable to promotion and restoration of the physical, mental and spiritual wellbeing in a planned manner. It is entire learning process during which the communities learn the skills and behavior for maintenance and improvement of health and wellbeing in a holistic manner through education processes. According to WHO, health is a state of complete physical, mental and social wellbeing and not merely the absence of disease and infirmity.

Scope of Health Education

The role of health education cannot be overlooked when it comes to building a healthy nation. The aim of health education is to sensitize the people about health awareness. The importance of health education: health education is of vital significance for formulation and implementation of health policies and programs; it is primarily needed to improve, maintain and restoration of health of community; to enhance the quality of life of people by increasing life expectancy and helping them to live long and healthy life; to reduce premature death and mortality rate; and to reduce chronic disease, awareness, prevention and cure.

The scope of health education is widespread and is of utmost important. Health education is a key factor in various socioeconomic fields such as home, schools and communities. Life at home is the foundation of the activities in a society. Healthy home leads to healthy society which in turn leads to great nation. Policy makers or health officials should train parents first about eating habits/ diet plans, physical health, cleanliness, etc. and then other members at home. Otherwise also, parents can train their children after having secured training from concerned officials. Schools or colleges are the hubs to train children / youngsters about health education. Government bodies or school authorities should include health education in their curriculum. They should collaborate with policy makers and health educators to train their students with reference to various parameters concerned to health: to keep good physical and mental health; healthy diet methods; methods to prevent diseases; drug and alcohol prevention; etc, so that the students in turn train people at their home or locality (society). Community health education is important for a society or nation. Healthy life style, disease prevention, environmental hygiene and cleanliness and dietary plans are some of the methods that improve a particular community or a community in general through health education.

Health Education and Economy

Poor quality of human health can adversely affect the economy of a country. As a part of human capital, if our masses will be unhealthy and unaware of health issues will lead a country to under investing in workforce productivity. It leads to vicious circle.

Human capital is significant determinant of economic prosperity and hence, health education is in need of an hour for growing economy that can be done by spreading learning and awareness about health restoration and maintenance. Health and economic development are both interrelated terms. Adverse effects of poor human capital due to lack of health awareness can be irreversible and grave. The effects can come in many faces as: poor economic growth; poor human capital index; increased mortality rates; poor social infrastructure; reduced per capita and national income; deficit in manpower supply; poor economic development due to poor factor productivity; increased unemployment and increased poverty and fall in living standards. Studies show that increased healthcare costs is due to limited literacy skills [1,2].

Methods to Improve Health Education

Improve access should be made to health information by the means of media in the

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form of increasing the media's awareness of health literacy issues and making scientific information easy to understand by public. It is also needed to develop new methods for information dissemination. Investment on public health is more effective and efficient when compared with other sources. Health authorities should work with educators to improve curriculum on health. Educators are the highly respected members of a society. Health care programs can be conducted in institutes, work places and community health centers. Policy makers and health educators should adapt health care system according to the need of their people locally but in addition to major health issues [3-5].

Health education should reach people living in different communities, region, etc. and the concerned health officials should monitor people whether people follow the rules and regulations that will enhance the life of people. Audio visual programs, seminars, workshops and conferences, visit to cities/ towns, villages, schools and homes will be reliable to improve health education.

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